

Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

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ABSTRACT: Indonesia is a country with high disaster vulnerability, including frequent landslides in various regions. One of the mitigation approaches being developed is the use of vetiver grass as a nature-based solution to strengthen soil stability. However, the success of implementing such mitigation programs depends not only on the technical effectiveness of the methods used but also on the ability of various actors to build collaboration in their execution. This study aims to analyze collaborative governance practices in the implementation of the vetiver planting program as a landslide mitigation effort in Banyumas Regency. This research uses a qualitative approach with data collection techniques through interviews, observation, and documentation. Research informants involve actors involved in the program, including the Banyumas Regency Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD), the Serayu Opak Progo Watershed Management Office (BPDAS), village governments, the community, and volunteer organizations. The results show that the implementation of the vetiver planting program involves the collaboration of various actors who play roles in the process of planning, implementation, and evaluation of activities. BPBD acts as a facilitator in building coordination between institutions, while the community and volunteer organizations contribute to the implementation of activities in the field. The findings of this study indicate that a collaborative governance approach can strengthen collective capacity in the implementation of nature-based solution disaster mitigation at the local level.

KEYWORDS: Collaborative Governance, Disaster Mitigation, Landslides, Vetiver, Banyumas

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the countries with high disaster vulnerability. Complex geographical conditions, diverse topography, and high rainfall intensity cause various regions in Indonesia to have the potential for natural disasters, including landslides. Landslides often occur in hilly areas and regions with high slope gradients, especially during the rainy season when the soil experiences water saturation.

Challenges in disaster risk reduction are not only related to the technical aspects of mitigation but also to how various actors can coordinate and collaborate in an effective disaster governance system (Ikeda & Nagasaka, 2011). Banyumas Regency is one of the areas with a fairly high potential for landslide vulnerability. Several village areas in Banyumas Regency have a history of recurring landslide events, thus requiring effective and sustainable mitigation efforts. Traditionally, landslide mitigation has generally been carried out through structural approaches such as the construction of retaining walls, gabions, or slope reinforcement. However, these approaches often require large costs and cannot always reach all areas with the potential for landslides.

As an alternative, vegetation-based mitigation approaches are being developed as part of non-structural mitigation strategies. One of the plants widely used in soil conservation efforts is vetiver. Vetiver is known for its strong root system that can hold soil movement, making it frequently used in erosion control and slope stabilization efforts (Truong & Loch, 2004). Therefore, this plant is seen as having potential as a non-structural mitigation solution in reducing landslide risk, particularly in regions with steep topography and high vulnerability.

In Banyumas Regency, the implementation of vetiver planting is carried out through cooperation between the Banyumas Regency Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) and the Serayu Opak Progo Watershed Management Office (BPDAS SOP). This program was born from communication between the two institutions, recognizing the potential for using vetiver as a landslide mitigation effort in the Banyumas region, which has high vulnerability.

In addition to involving these two agencies, the vetiver planting program also engages village governments and the local community. The involvement of these diverse actors indicates collaborative practices in implementing disaster mitigation policies. Within the field of public administration, such practices can be analyzed through the lens of collaborative governance, which underscores the importance of cooperation among actors in addressing public issues.

Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

Previous research has demonstrated that vetiver grass is effective in strengthening soil structure and reducing the potential for erosion and landslides due to its deep and robust root system (Truong & Loch, 2004; Morgan, 2005). However, most of these studies focus primarily on the technical and ecological dimensions of vetiver use in soil conservation. Meanwhile, the governance aspects and the collaborative processes among actors in implementing vegetation-based mitigation programs remain relatively underexplored in public policy and administrative research. In reality, the success of disaster mitigation programs depends not only on the technical efficacy of a particular method but also on the ability of various stakeholders to establish effective collaboration throughout the planning, implementation, and evaluation phases. Thus, this research seeks to examine how collaborative governance practices are established in the implementation of the vetiver planting program as a landslide mitigation effort in Banyumas Regency.

In the context of Indonesian disaster policy, the collaborative governance approach is increasingly seen as essential, as the complexity of disaster management requires the involvement of multiple government agencies, social organizations, and local communities (Rahmayanti, 2021). Against this backdrop, this study aims to analyze collaborative governance practices in the implementation of the vetiver planting program as a landslide disaster mitigation effort in Banyumas Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on landslide disaster mitigation has evolved through various approaches, encompassing both structural and non-structural strategies. Structural approaches typically involve the construction of physical infrastructure, such as retaining walls (talud), gabions, and slope reinforcement to stabilize soil movement. However, numerous studies indicate that structural approaches often require significant costs and face limitations in covering extensive disaster-prone areas (Sudibyakto, 2011). Consequently, non-structural mitigation approaches have begun to receive greater attention in disaster studies.

One emerging approach is ecosystem-based mitigation. This approach emphasizes leveraging the ecological functions of the environment to reduce disaster risks. Vegetation plays a crucial role in maintaining soil stability, as root systems enhance soil cohesion and minimize erosion potential (Morgan, 2005). In the context of landslide mitigation, the use of specific vegetation has been widely recommended as an effective and sustainable soil conservation method.

One plant frequently utilized in soil conservation is vetiver (*Chrysopogon zizanioides*). Vetiver grass possesses an exceptionally deep and robust root system capable of reinforcing soil structure and enhancing slope stability. Truong and Loch (2004) explain that vetiver roots can grow to depths exceeding three meters, thereby functioning as natural soil reinforcement. Furthermore, vetiver exhibits high adaptability to various environmental conditions, leading to its widespread use in land rehabilitation and erosion control programs globally.

In Indonesia, the application of vetiver for soil conservation has been implemented in several regions as part of erosion control and landslide mitigation strategies. Several studies indicate that vetiver planting can serve as a relatively inexpensive and easily implementable nature-based solution (NBS) for community-based disaster mitigation (Kapucu, 2012). Nevertheless, the successful implementation of vegetation-based mitigation programs is determined not only by the plant's technical properties but also by institutional factors and community participation.

In the context of disaster risk reduction (DRR), local community involvement is a vital element in ensuring the sustainability of mitigation programs. The community-based disaster risk reduction (CBDRR) approach emphasizes that the community should be positioned not merely as beneficiaries but as active actors in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of disaster mitigation programs (Kapucu, 2012). The involvement of various local actors, including volunteer organizations and community groups, can strengthen collective capacity in facing disaster risks while enhancing the effectiveness of mitigation policy implementation at the local level. Community involvement is critical because it increases community capacity to face disaster threats collectively (Kapucu & Sadiq, 2016). In many cases, the success of DRR programs largely depends on the government's ability to foster inclusive collaboration with the community and various non-governmental organizations concerned with disaster issues.

From a public administration perspective, the implementation of disaster mitigation policies often involves multiple actors with distinct roles. Therefore, the collaborative governance approach has become a prominent perspective to understand how various actors work together to solve complex public problems. Ansell and Gash (2008) define collaborative governance as a decision-making process involving multiple stakeholders—both governmental and non-governmental—within a shared forum to achieve public goals.

Various studies show that inter-agency collaboration can improve the effectiveness of disaster management. Collaboration facilitates resource coordination, information exchange, and clearer role distribution among the involved actors (Emerson & Nabatchi, 2015). In the context of local disaster mitigation, cooperation between local governments, technical agencies, village governments, and the community is a crucial factor in enhancing disaster mitigation capacity.

While various studies have discussed vegetation-based disaster mitigation and collaborative governance practices, research specifically linking these two aspects remains relatively limited. Most research on vetiver focuses on the technical aspects of soil

Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

conservation and slope stabilization, whereas collaborative governance studies typically address institutional dynamics in general public policy.

Consequently, this research seeks to fill this gap by analyzing the implementation of the vetiver planting program as a landslide disaster mitigation effort through the perspective of collaborative governance. By examining how various actors are involved in the planning, execution, and maintenance of vetiver planting programs in Banyumas Regency, this study is expected to contribute to the development of ecology-based disaster mitigation studies within the field of public administration.

TEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study employs a collaborative governance perspective to analyze the implementation of the vetiver planting program as a landslide disaster mitigation effort in Banyumas Regency. This approach was selected because disaster management represents a complex public issue that cannot be addressed by a single institution alone. Effective disaster mitigation necessitates the involvement of diverse stakeholders, ranging from government bodies and technical agencies to local administrations and the general public.

The concept of collaborative governance has been extensively discussed in public administration literature as an approach to addressing cross-sectoral public issues. Ansell and Gash (2008) define collaborative governance as a decision-making process that involves various stakeholders in a formal, consensus-oriented shared forum, aiming to formulate or implement public policy. Within this framework, the government is no longer the sole policy determinant but rather acts as a facilitator that coordinates various interests.

The collaborative governance model developed by Ansell and Gash emphasizes that successful collaboration is influenced by several key factors: starting conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership, and the collaborative process itself. Starting conditions involve trust levels among actors, resource distribution, and the historical relationships between the involved agencies. Meanwhile, institutional design refers to the rules and mechanisms that govern how the collaborative process is conducted (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

Furthermore, the collaborative process is significantly influenced by facilitative leadership, which is capable of fostering communication, trust, and commitment among participants. This leadership style plays a vital role in promoting constructive dialogue, allowing various parties to work toward common objectives. In practice, collaboration typically unfolds through sustained interactions such as face-to-face dialogue, negotiation processes, and trust-building efforts between the parties involved.

The evolution of the collaborative governance concept is further elucidated by Emerson and Nabatchi (2015) through the 'Collaborative Governance Regime' framework. They posit that collaboration in public policy constitutes a system where multiple actors work together to achieve collective goals through continuous interaction dynamics. Under this framework, collaboration is understood not merely as a simple coordination process, but as a governance mechanism involving interaction dynamics, mutual learning, and shared responsibility among actors.

In the context of disaster management, the collaborative governance approach is highly relevant, as disaster risk management requires coordination between various agencies with differing resources and authorities. Previous research indicates that inter-agency collaboration can enhance the effectiveness of disaster response through resource integration, improved coordination, and strengthened institutional capacity (Kapucu, 2012). Moreover, collaboration enables community engagement in the mitigation process, thereby increasing the sustainability of the programs.

In this study, the concept of collaborative governance is utilized to analyze how various actors are involved in the implementation of the vetiver planting program in Banyumas Regency. The stakeholders involved in the program include the Banyumas Regency Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD), the Serayu Opak Progo Watershed Management Office (BPDAS SOP), village governments, and the local community. Each actor fulfills a distinct role in the planning, execution, and maintenance phases of this vegetation-based mitigation program. By applying the collaborative governance framework, this research seeks to explain how the collaborative process among actors was formed, the specific roles of each agency in program implementation, and how community involvement contributes to the success of landslide mitigation through vetiver planting in Banyumas Regency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative approach to gain an in-depth understanding of the inter-agency collaboration process in implementing the landslide disaster mitigation program through vetiver planting in Banyumas Regency. A qualitative approach was selected as the research focuses on the interaction processes between actors, the dynamics of cooperation, and the experiences of stakeholders involved in the execution of the mitigation program.

Qualitative research methods allow for a comprehensive exploration of social phenomena within their real-world contexts. In public policy research, this approach is frequently utilized to understand how a policy or program is implemented by various actors with differing roles and interests (Creswell, 2014).

Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

The research was conducted in Banyumas Regency, Central Java, which is characterized by a high level of landslide susceptibility. A specific focus was placed on Banjarsari Wetan Village, which has a history of landslide events and serves as a site for the implementation of the vetiver planting program as a vegetation-based mitigation effort.

Data sources for this study consist of primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained through interviews with parties involved in the program's execution, namely the Banyumas Regency Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) and the Serayu Opak Progo Watershed Management Office (BPDAS SOP). Interviews were conducted to elicit information regarding the program planning process, inter-agency coordination mechanisms, and the field execution of vetiver planting activities. Additionally, the study utilizes secondary data retrieved from official documents, activity reports, and literature related to disaster mitigation and landslide risk management. These secondary data serve to strengthen the analysis and provide a more comprehensive overview of the research context.

Informants were selected using purposive sampling, considering their direct involvement in the vetiver planting program in Banyumas Regency. The research informants include key actors such as representatives from BPBD Banyumas, BPDAS Serayu Opak Progo, village governments, and community members involved in the planting activities. Furthermore, the study incorporates perspectives from volunteer organizations participating in disaster mitigation efforts in the region.

Data collection techniques include in-depth interviews and documentary analysis. Interviews were conducted directly with key informants possessing relevant knowledge and involvement in the mitigation program. Meanwhile, the documentary study involved reviewing various documents pertaining to the execution of the vetiver planting program in Banyumas Regency.

To ensure data validity, the study employed source and method triangulation techniques. Source triangulation was achieved by comparing information obtained from various informants involved in the program. Method triangulation was performed by combining data from interviews, field observations, and documentation related to the landslide mitigation program. Through this triangulation process, the researchers sought to ensure that the data achieved an adequate level of accuracy and consistency.

Data analysis in this study follows qualitative techniques comprising three main stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. Data reduction involved selecting and simplifying the information obtained from interviews and documentation. Subsequently, the reduced data were presented in a descriptive narrative to facilitate the analytical process. The final stage involved drawing conclusions by interpreting the research findings based on the collaborative governance theoretical framework employed in this study (Miles, Huberman, & Saldaña, 2014).

Through this methodological approach, the research is expected to provide a deeper understanding of how inter-agency collaboration is formed in the implementation of vegetation-based disaster mitigation programs and the roles of each actor in supporting the program's success in Banyumas Regency.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

1. Collaborative Initiation in Landslide Mitigation Efforts

Landslide disaster mitigation efforts in Banyumas Regency through vetiver planting did not emerge spontaneously; rather, they originated from proactive communication and collaborative initiatives between government agencies possessing distinct authorities and capacities. Based on interviews with representatives from the Serayu Opak Progo Watershed Management Office (BPDAS SOP), the idea to implement vetiver planting in Banyumas was informed by prior experiences in applying similar methods across various other regions in Indonesia. These vetiver planting practices have been established in several areas as part of broader soil conservation and vegetation-based disaster mitigation efforts.

Vetiver is widely recognized for its robust root system, which is capable of stabilizing soil movement, making it a frequent choice for erosion control and slope stabilization (Truong & Loch, 2004). Consequently, this plant is regarded as a potential non-structural mitigation solution for reducing landslide risks, particularly in regions characterized by steep topography and high vulnerability.

In the context of mitigation in Banyumas Regency, initial communication regarding the program's potential implementation occurred between the Banyumas Regency Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) and BPDAS SOP. As the agency with the primary authority for disaster management at the regional level, BPBD possesses critical data and mapping regarding areas with high landslide susceptibility. Meanwhile, BPDAS SOP holds the necessary technical expertise in soil conservation and watershed management.

The collaboration established between these two agencies reflects collaborative governance practices, wherein various governmental actors work together to address complex public issues (Ansell & Gash, 2008). In this instance, landslide mitigation is viewed not merely as the responsibility of a single institution, but as a collective endeavor that necessitates the integration of knowledge, resources, and authority from diverse stakeholders.

2. Determination of Priority Locations for Vetiver Planting

An important stage in the implementation of this mitigation program is the determination of priority locations for vetiver planting. Based on interviews with officials from the Banyumas Regency Disaster Management Agency (BPBD), the process of site selection was conducted by BPBD, as the agency possesses disaster risk data and hazard mapping for the region. BPBD identified villages

Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

that have a history of landslide occurrences and high vulnerability levels. One of the villages selected as the program implementation site was Tlaga Village. This village was chosen due to its relatively high frequency of landslide incidents, making it a priority area that requires additional mitigation measures.

In the process of determining the location, the Serayu Opak Progo Watershed Management Agency (BPDAS SOP) generally relied on the recommendations provided by BPBD Banyumas. This reliance is largely due to BPBD's more comprehensive understanding of disaster vulnerability conditions within its jurisdiction. Consequently, decisions regarding priority locations for vetiver planting were primarily based on BPBD's assessment. Nevertheless, coordination between the two institutions continued during the program implementation stage. The trust placed by BPDAS SOP in BPBD's recommendations reflects an established cooperative relationship between the two institutions.

Joint field surveys were mainly conducted during the monitoring and evaluation phase of the program. In this stage, BPBD and BPDAS SOP jointly monitored the growth of vetiver plants as well as the slope conditions in the planting areas. These monitoring activities aimed to assess plant development and evaluate the effectiveness of the vegetation-based mitigation measures that had been implemented.

From a collaborative governance perspective, this practice illustrates a division of roles based on the respective capacities and authorities of the institutions involved. BPBD played a role in determining priority locations based on disaster risk levels, while BPDAS SOP provided technical support in program implementation and participated in evaluating the outcomes of the activities. This pattern of cooperation reflects an inter-organizational coordination mechanism in which institutions complement one another in disaster risk management (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

3. Community Involvement in the Implementation Process

In addition to government institutions, the implementation of the vetiver planting program also involved local communities. Community involvement became an important aspect because part of the land used for planting belonged to local residents. Prior to the planting activities, the village government, together with BPBD, conducted communication and socialization activities with the community regarding the objectives and benefits of the program. Residents were informed about the function of vetiver in reinforcing soil stability as well as its potential benefits in reducing landslide risks in their surrounding environment. This process was important to ensure that landowners provided consent before the planting activities were carried out.

Following the socialization process, community members were actively involved in the vetiver planting activities at the designated locations. Community participation occurred not only during the implementation stage but also during the maintenance phase after planting had taken place. Based on interviews with the informants, local residents played a role in maintaining the vetiver plants to ensure that they could grow properly.

In addition to local communities, the vetiver planting activities also involved several disaster-related volunteer organizations operating in Banyumas Regency. These organizations included the Indonesian Red Cross (Palang Merah Indonesia – PMI), the National Zakat Agency through its disaster response program (Baznas Tanggap Bencana), the Muhammadiyah Disaster Management Center (MDMC), and Taruna Siaga Bencana (TAGANA). These organizations participated in the vetiver planting activities alongside local government agencies and community members as part of a community-based disaster mitigation effort.

The involvement of volunteer organizations in these mitigation activities indicates that disaster management efforts do not solely focus on post-disaster response but also include preventive measures through mitigation initiatives. Collaboration among local government institutions, community members, and volunteer organizations enables broader mobilization of human resources and strengthens the capacity for implementing mitigation programs at the local level.

Previous studies have highlighted that effective disaster risk reduction requires collaborative governance systems involving multiple actors across sectors and levels of government (Chaudhary et al., 2021). From the perspective of collaborative governance, the involvement of communities and volunteer organizations reflects cross-sector collaboration between government institutions and civil society in managing disaster risks. The participation of these various actors plays an important role in supporting the successful implementation of vegetation-based mitigation programs through vetiver planting in Banyumas Regency.

4. Program Implementation and Evaluation

The implementation of the vetiver planting program in Banyumas Regency indicates that the plants have grown well in the designated locations. However, the effectiveness of vetiver in reducing landslide risks still requires further investigation, as its impact on slope stability typically takes time to become significantly observable.

The program was not implemented as a one-time activity. Based on information obtained from the informants, the vetiver planting initiative is planned to be expanded to several other villages in the following year. This indicates that the program is perceived to have the potential to be further developed as part of the region's disaster mitigation strategy. Periodic evaluations of the program are conducted through field surveys involving both BPBD and BPDAS SOP. These evaluation activities aim to monitor the growth of vetiver plants and assess the effectiveness of the program over a certain period of time. The evaluation process also serves as a platform for both institutions to improve implementation methods for future activities.

Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

Within the framework of collaborative governance, this joint evaluation process demonstrates the presence of an inter-organizational learning mechanism. Collaboration occurs not only during the implementation phase but also through reflection and efforts to improve the quality of the program. Such processes of collective learning represent one of the key characteristics of collaborative governance systems (Emerson & Nabatchi, 2015).

5. Collaborative Governance Dynamics in Vetiver-Based Landslide Mitigation

From the perspective of collaborative governance, starting conditions represent an important factor influencing the formation of collaboration among actors. In the context of landslide mitigation in Banyumas Regency, the initial conditions that encouraged collaboration were the high level of regional vulnerability to landslides and the limited resources available to the local government to address the problem independently. These conditions prompted the Banyumas Regency Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) to establish cooperation with various stakeholders, including the Serayu Opak Watershed Management Agency (BPDAS SOP), village governments, local communities, and volunteer organizations concerned with disaster management. This situation of disaster vulnerability became a driving factor for multiple actors to engage collectively in mitigation efforts.

Facilitative leadership can also be observed in the role of BPBD Banyumas, which acted as a key coordinating actor in fostering inter-organizational collaboration. BPBD not only initiated the vetiver planting program but also facilitated communication among village governments, BPDAS SOP, local communities, and various volunteer organizations. Through this facilitative role, BPBD created a coordination space that enabled different actors to contribute according to their respective capacities in the effort to mitigate landslide risks.

The collaborative process within the vetiver planting program is also reflected in the involvement of multiple actors in the implementation of field activities. In addition to local communities, the planting activities involved several volunteer organizations, including the Indonesian Red Cross (PMI), the Muhammadiyah Disaster Management Center (MDMC), Bagana, and Baznas Tanggap Bencana. The participation of these organizations demonstrates the presence of multi-actor engagement in the implementation of disaster mitigation programs. Such collaboration not only strengthens the capacity to carry out vetiver planting activities but also fosters a process of collective learning among the actors involved in disaster risk reduction at the local level.

6. Interregional Collaboration in Disaster Response

In addition to collaboration within vegetation-based mitigation programs, inter-institutional cooperation was also evident in the context of direct disaster response. According to information provided by the Head of Division at the Banyumas Regency Disaster Management Agency (BPBD), cooperation has also occurred between BPBD Banyumas and BPBD Banjarnegara during emergency landslide situations. In 2024, a landslide occurred in Banjarsari Wetan Village that required the evacuation of landslide debris. In this situation, BPBD Banyumas faced limitations in the availability of heavy equipment required for disaster response operations. To address this limitation, BPBD Banjarnegara provided assistance by deploying heavy equipment to support the evacuation process.

This inter-regional cooperation demonstrates that collaboration in disaster management occurs not only in mitigation programs but also in the context of emergency response. During disaster situations, the resource limitations faced by a particular region can be addressed through cooperation with neighboring regions. This phenomenon reflects the importance of collaborative networks among government institutions within disaster management systems. Through such cooperation, local governments are able to support one another in responding to crisis situations that require rapid action and adequate resources (Kapucu, 2012).

In the Indonesian context, the practice of collaborative governance in disaster management has increasingly developed through the involvement of various government institutions and non-governmental organizations in mitigation and disaster response efforts (Khafian, 2023). Overall, the findings of this study indicate that the implementation of landslide mitigation through vetiver planting in Banyumas Regency is the result of collaborative processes involving government institutions and local communities. This collaboration includes a clear division of roles among BPBD, BPDAS Serayu Opak Progo, village governments, and local communities across various stages of the program, ranging from planning and implementation to evaluation. Such a collaborative approach enables the integration of knowledge and resources from multiple actors, allowing the mitigation program to be implemented more effectively and sustainably.

This study has several limitations. The research data were obtained from a limited number of informants and focused on a single case of mitigation program implementation in Banyumas Regency. Therefore, the findings of this study cannot yet be generalized to other regions with different characteristics.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyze the implementation of a landslide disaster mitigation program through vetiver planting in Banyumas Regency using a collaborative governance perspective. The findings indicate that the implementation of the program is the result of collaboration among multiple actors with different roles and capacities in disaster management.

Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

The primary collaboration in this program occurs between the Banyumas Regency Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) and the Serayu Opak Watershed Management Agency (BPDAS SOP). BPBD plays a role in determining priority locations in landslide-prone areas based on disaster risk mapping within the region, while BPDAS SOP provides technical support in implementing soil conservation methods through vetiver planting. The cooperation between these institutions demonstrates a division of roles based on their respective institutional capacities.

In addition to intergovernmental collaboration, the implementation of the program also involves local communities as landowners and as actors responsible for maintaining the vetiver plants after the planting activities have been completed. Community participation thus becomes a key factor in supporting the sustainability of vegetation-based mitigation programs.

Furthermore, the mitigation activities also involve various disaster volunteer organizations that participate in vetiver planting activities. The involvement of volunteer organizations indicates that disaster management at the local level does not rely solely on governmental capacity but also involves contributions from civil society.

The findings of this study suggest that a collaborative governance approach can serve as an effective strategy for disaster risk management, particularly in the implementation of community-based mitigation programs. Collaboration among local governments, technical institutions, communities, and volunteer organizations enables the integration of resources, knowledge, and broader participation in disaster risk reduction efforts.

This study also highlights that disaster mitigation efforts are not limited to the development of physical infrastructure but can also be implemented through ecological approaches such as vetiver planting. Therefore, strengthening collaboration among actors and increasing community participation are crucial factors in supporting the success of sustainable disaster mitigation programs at the local level.

This research contributes to the field of public administration, particularly in the study of collaborative governance in disaster risk reduction. The findings show that the success of vegetation-based mitigation programs is determined not only by the technical effectiveness of vetiver plants in reinforcing soil structure but also by the ability of various actors to establish effective collaboration. The collaboration among BPBD, BPDAS, village governments, local communities, and volunteer organizations demonstrates that a collaborative approach to disaster mitigation can enhance collective capacity in addressing disaster risks at the local level.

From a practical perspective, the findings emphasize the importance of strengthening collaborative mechanisms among institutions in the implementation of nature-based disaster mitigation programs. Local governments can optimize the roles of various stakeholders, including community groups and volunteer organizations, in supporting sustainable mitigation initiatives. However, this study has limitations as it focuses on a single case study in Banyumas Regency. Future research may therefore examine collaborative governance practices in disaster mitigation programs in other regions in order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of collaboration dynamics in disaster risk reduction.

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Collaborative Governance in Landslide Mitigation through Vetiver Planting Programs in Banyumas Regency

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